

SMART ERA PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

SMART ERA CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN RURAL INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT

Designing and implementing socio-technical innovations to tackle rural development issues is a complex and multifaceted process. The EU-funded SMART ERA project addresses this challenge by empowering local communities to actively engage in creating innovative solutions tailored to their unique needs. **A co-design toolkit has been developed to involve local stakeholders in creating Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs)-customised solutions** combining both technological and non-technological components **to address rural challenges**. To support this process, the toolkit identifies **key 'ingredients' -social, economic, technological, political, and infrastructural elements-** essential for designing effective interventions. The co-design toolkit includes both analog and digital components.

The analog toolkit **includes** ingredient **information cards, reflection prompts, support canvases,** and a **visual progress tracking board**. These resources encourage critical reflection on rural communities' needs, available resources, and transformative capacities.

The digital component complements the analog tool by providing real-time monitoring, asynchronous collaboration, and gamified engagement. It integrates a digital version of the tracking board, visual feedback, and recognition mechanisms, allowing communities to co-create SIPs in a flexible environment. By combining digital efficiency with analog strengths, the toolkit enhances accessibility, participatory governance, and community resilience, contributing to sustainable rural development and autonomous rural initiatives.

Practical implications: The co-design toolkit is offered to **organisations** who steer the community engagement processes to help them **guide sessions with rural communities** and help them assess their needs, resources, and desired solutions through co-design workshops, inter-sectoral dialogue, and creative envisioning. Currently **supported languages** are Bulgarian, English, Finnish, Italian, Serbian, Slovenian and Spanish.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Complementarity with other methods:

- The toolkit complements established, general-purpose, co-design and community-led approaches by providing **tailored materials** that focus on the key dimensions of rural innovation.
- Rather than aiming to be exhaustive, the toolkit provides a **structured methodology** for categorising and illustrating potential ingredients. Users are encouraged to **build upon it** with their own ideas, insights, and local knowledge.

Obstacles:

- Innovation is a **long-term**, incremental process—often unfolding through iterative cycles.
- **No single co-design pathway can suit every territory** or rural challenge.

Overcoming obstacles and accommodating different contexts:

- The toolkit avoids prescribing a one-size-fits-all model. Instead, it offers both **inspiration and practical guidance** to help rural communities assemble suites of technological and non-technological “ingredients” that are **adapted to** their unique **contexts**.
- Designed for **flexibility and adaptability**, the toolkit supports diverse design journeys and development paces. It can be used across a range of settings, from formal institutional frameworks to informal grassroots initiatives.

Open development for future extensions:

The toolkit is conceived as a **living resource** that can evolve over time by incorporating feedback and new materials aligned with the goals and structure of the innovation process. Its value lies not only in the content it provides, but also in its adaptability and potential to be shaped and integrated with familiar local approaches and methodologies. **Community ownership and creative adaptation** are therefore essential to fully unlock its potential.

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

[Deliverable D3.1 “SIP Co-Design Toolkit”](#)

